

Building citizenship from school: The role of education in political socialization and citizen participation

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This article presents a systematic review of recent literature to examine how education contributes to the formation of young people as political subjects. Applying PRISMA guidelines, studies published between 2018 and 2023 in databases and search engines ProQuest, Scopus, ScienceDirect, and The Lens were selected. The review covers five main categories: political socialization in school contexts, civic education and citizen participation, pedagogical strategies and educational methodologies, educational policies and sociopolitical structures, and training for social justice in educational contexts. The findings reveal that schools not only transmit civic knowledge but also serve as spaces for the negotiation of political meanings and the construction of active citizenship. However, limitations were identified in the reviewed studies, such as the lack of generalizability due to the majority selection of qualitative and contextual approaches, and the absence of longitudinal data necessary to evaluate the long-term effects of educational interventions. It is suggested that future research include mixed methodologies and comparative approaches to obtain a more diverse and generalizable understanding of educational processes in citizenship formation.

Keywords: Citizenship, Education, Political socialization, Citizen participation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Political formation among young schoolchildren has become an increasingly relevant topic in the social and educational sciences. Schools are not only spaces for academic learning, but also scenarios where the first experiences of political participation and construction of civic identity take place.

In this sense, school contexts act as microcosms of society, where daily interactions, educational practices, and institutional discourses participate in the configuration of students' political attitudes and civic awareness [1, 2].

Contemporary academic literature on political socialization suggests that young people not only acquire civic knowledge in classrooms but also actively engage in negotiating and reinterpreting the political meanings that surround them [3, 4]. Theorists such as Pierre Rosanvallon and Ernesto Laclau have worked to understand these processes by proposing that politics is largely a field of symbolic contestation and collective meaning-making. Rosanvallon sees democracy as a space of social learning that is shaped by the process of political change. Extends beyond formal institutions [5], while Laclau highlights the importance of the articulation of demands and meanings in the formation of political identities [6].

These theoretical perspectives complement empirical studies that have demonstrated how schools can foster critical and participatory citizenship. For example, programs that promote open debate and collaborative activities are effective in developing critical thinking skills and fostering greater civic engagement among young people [7, 8]. However, the implementation of these strategies faces limitations such as institutional resistance and lack of resources, which often restrict schools' ability to adopt more inclusive and democratic pedagogical approaches [9, 10].

This literature review examines how schools can function as spaces for the construction of active and engaged citizenship, analyzing the pedagogical practices, socialization contexts, and educational policies that influence the political formation of young people. Through this analysis, the main trends and approaches in current research are identified, as well as the dynamics that shape the construction of politics in contemporary societies.

2. METHOD

For the development of this work, a systematic review was carried out following the PRISMA guidelines [11] on the scientific contributions published in the field of the formation of the political subject and the construction of citizenship.

2.1 Systematic search

The inquiries were carried out between September 2023 and March 2024. A search equation was constructed that included terms such as political subject, school, and citizenship, using Boolean operators AND and OR. The systematic search was carried out in the databases and search engines Proquest, Scopus, ScienceDirect, and The Lens. The period for research publications was delimited from 2018 to the present; in the case of doctoral theses, the last 10 years were considered.

2.2 Inclusion criteria

- Document type: scientific journal articles and doctoral theses.
- Language: English and Spanish
- Relevance and focus: studies that address the topic of interest.
- Direct relevance: studies that address the concepts of construction of the political subject, construction of citizenship, and democracy in schools.
- Quality and rigor: publications in high-impact international journals, peer-reviewed.
- Relevant disciplines: political science, humanities, and social sciences.

2.3 Exclusion criteria

- Duplicate documents: duplicate documents were eliminated considering that the information search was carried out in four databases.
- Insufficient or superficial content on the topic of interest.
- Studies that lack supported information.

Following these guidelines, 18 duplicate publications were eliminated, and a selection was made by title, considering 120 articles relevant. After reading the abstracts, 85 articles were discarded, and 38 studies were identified as meeting the inclusion criteria defined for the systematic review phase.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The literature review has been structured into five key categories that encompass the different approaches, results, methodologies, and limitations of studies on the construction of politics among young schoolchildren. These categories are political socialization and school contexts; civic education and citizen participation among young people; pedagogical strategies and educational methodologies for civic education; educational policies and sociopolitical structures: influences on citizenship education; and towards a critical consciousness: education for social justice in educational contexts. This organization allows for a structured view of the main debates in the field.

3.1 Political socialization and school contexts

Political socialization in school contexts encompasses a series of studies that explore how educational environments and social interactions influence the formation of young people's political subjectivity. These works show that political socialization processes are not limited to direct participation in civic activities, but are also manifested in the way in which students internalize and question established power structures, thus shaping their political identities.

For example, [12] indicates that in Germany, urbanization and purchasing power have no direct implication on students' future political attitudes. However, young people in contexts with greater opportunities for political participation show less interest in participating in electoral processes, leaning more towards illegal forms of protest. This suggests that there is a disillusionment with traditional forms of political participation and that a reconsideration of the importance of socialization contexts in shaping political attitudes is required.

In [2, 13] the processes of subjectivization that emerge in spaces of socialization are addressed, manifesting themselves in narratives of self-definition and the questioning of the status quo. Both studies highlight that socialization in school contexts is fundamental for the construction of political identities that challenge established norms.

[14] delves deeper into this discussion by analyzing how children's political subjectivities are shaped through their interactions with culture, language, and narratives, even in contexts of violence and conflict. This study highlights the relevance of early socialization in school settings and how these contexts durably shape students' political attitudes. [15] contributes to the debate with a gender perspective, showing that there are significant differences in political socialization among boys. Girls show a greater tendency towards obedience and associate the act of voting with compliance with norms, which could influence their future civic participation. This study suggests that gender-differentiated educational experiences in the school setting may have significant implications for the formation of political attitudes.

Studies such as [3] in the UK investigate how political knowledge and attitudes in children develop as they grow up. Their study shows that, with age, children acquire more political knowledge, but also develop more critical attitudes towards their representatives. This highlights the significant role of the educational environment in the early development of political awareness and critical attitude towards authority figures.

[16] provides a perspective on how young people construct their political identity through their school experiences, pointing out the contradictions that arise when education, conceived as a tool for the construction of subjectivities, also acts as a constraint under neoliberal policies that favor individualism and competition. This study highlights the complexity of political socialization in educational contexts, where institutional narratives and educational policies can have both liberating and restrictive effects on the formation of political subjectivity.

[1] analyzes how participation in volunteer programs within schools influences the formation of political attitudes and the political socialization of students. This study highlights that, while male participants tend to show greater favorability towards political participation, school activities also play a crucial role in shaping political attitudes and community integration of young people, suggesting that socialization in school contexts may vary significantly by gender.

Finally, discourses and technologies also impact the formation of political subjectivities in school contexts. [4, 17]. While [4] analyzes how teachers, recognized as essential actors in the educational process, shape the political imaginaries of students, [17] underlines that political and social experiences in schools are fundamental for the formation of political subjectivity, fostering social movements and critical knowledge.

Taken together, these studies demonstrate that school contexts play an essential role in political socialization, not only as spaces for the transmission of knowledge but also as scenarios where critical subjectivities are formed and political attitudes are shaped. Thus, schools are presented as vital places for the development of active and committed citizenship, where daily interactions, institutional discourses, and educational experiences contribute to the construction of students' political identity.

3.2 Conclusions from political socialization and school contexts

Research in this category shows that political subjectivization processes in secondary school students arise as a response to the power dynamics and norms established in educational contexts. The findings reveal that students develop political subjectivities, and therefore their socialization processes, through the expression of dissatisfaction and critical reflexivity towards the existing school order. This construction of subjectivity is seen as a form of political action that challenges authoritarian practices and discourses in schools, allowing young people to question and redefine their everyday reality.

A significant limitation of these studies is their interpretive and contextual nature, which makes it difficult to generalize the results to other school settings. Furthermore, the reliance on qualitative data may limit the possibility of quantitatively measuring the extent of these processes of political subjectivization among different student groups.

3.3 Civic education and citizen participation among young people

Civic education has been positioned as an essential component in the formation of active citizens capable of participating in an informed and critical manner in democratic processes. In this context, several studies have explored how educational programs, curricular policies, and school environments influence the development of civic attitudes and political participation of young people. These studies examine everything from the relationship between political knowledge and electoral participation to the influence of a democratic school climate on the construction of civic identities. A review of this literature provides a comprehensive view of how education can participate in the formation of citizens who have the skills required by contemporary democratic societies.

In [18] the role of the child in democratic politics is highlighted because, although children are formally excluded from voting and are represented by adults, they play a significant role in political processes. This approach highlights the need to consider young people as important actors in democracies and highlights the importance of their early civic education to develop informed and active citizens. Concerning the interest of young people in politics and their level of knowledge on civic issues, various studies have identified a relationship between civic education and citizen participation. [19] reveals that there is a direct correlation

between political ignorance and disinterest in participation; young people with less knowledge of political issues show less interest in participatory processes, including electoral ones.

This connection suggests that strengthening political education could be an effective way to increase civic engagement. [19] supports this perspective, highlighting that when political education is designed and implemented reflectively and contextually, its impact can be significant, demonstrating that the construction and appropriation of political knowledge, discussed in spaces with ideological diversity, not only increases interest in political issues but also facilitates a broader understanding of life in society.

Similarly, in [20] it is argued that a democratic school climate is important in promoting civic and political action. In a school environment where classes are conceived as spaces for open discussions, fair treatment, and equal participation, there is a tendency for hierarchical relationships between teachers and students to disappear. This approach encourages civic learning and critical thinking, suggesting that student autonomy is necessary for young people to see themselves and others as civic actors.

The transformation of the concept of citizenship is a recurring theme in recent research. [21] examines the case of Finland, where an attempt is made to reduce the emphasis on the nationalist notion of citizen to promote the idea of a global citizen. This linguistic and conceptual shift is significant, as it influences how citizenship is perceived and potentially expands the understanding towards maximal citizenship, encompassing a more inclusive and global approach.

In line with this transformation of citizenship, [22] examines how, since the 19th and 20th centuries, education has been seen as a means of preparing children as citizens of liberal societies. In this study, it is argued that the idea of childhood citizenship assigned to children in modernity reflects an effort to mold citizens who can perpetuate the values and structures of liberal societies, which underlines the normative function of civic education in different historical contexts.

On the other hand, the influence of educational policies on citizenship education is addressed in [23] where it is explored how in Chile educational policies do not fully reflect neoliberal political and social dynamics. Despite teachers' criticism of the neoliberal system, they face restrictions on their autonomy and citizenship education due to the authoritarian structures present in the school environment. This phenomenon poses a challenge for schools as key spaces for developing knowledge and practices that counteract the neoliberal model.

In Finland, [8] analyses a civic education course, concluding that teaching tends to perpetuate ideas of youth adaptation towards democratic participation, rather than transforming existing political structures. This approach highlights the need to redefine young people's political agency, not only in terms of participation but also in how they are recognized and act as political actors within their contexts.

Finally, [24] highlights that conventional interpretations of democracy, which do not sufficiently address equity or social justice, require a reconfiguration towards a more interdisciplinary education that promotes global citizenship and social justice. In this sense, civic education should not only prepare students to be informed citizens, but also critical and committed to social transformation. Taken together, these studies emphasize the importance of a comprehensive and critical civic education that fosters active participation and the development of conscious global citizens. Civic education, when approached inclusively and reflectively, can be a driver for social change and democratic participation.

3.4 Conclusions on civic education and citizen participation among young people

The reviewed studies reveal that civic education is instrumental in fostering young people's political interest and participation. Some, through mixed methodologies, including quantitative surveys and qualitative focus groups, have shown that collaborative learning strategies and an open classroom climate can significantly increase political knowledge and interest in politics. These educational approaches not only help mitigate political apathy but also compensate for disparities in political socialization arising from different family backgrounds.

However, it is important to consider some limitations in these studies. The ability to generalize the results to other contexts is limited by cultural and educational differences, and the sustained impact of these interventions over the long term remains unclear. Despite these limitations, the findings suggest that inclusive and participatory civic education is critical to preparing young people for active citizen participation, highlighting the need for pedagogical approaches that promote meaningful and engaged learning.

3.5 Pedagogical strategies and educational methodologies for civic education

The studies explore how different pedagogical practices influence students' political and civic education. Through the analysis of various educational methodologies, the research highlights not only the capacity of these strategies to foster critical thinking and active participation in political issues but also the limitations they face due to contextual and structural factors in school environments. The effectiveness of these practices depends largely on how they are implemented and the context in which they are developed, suggesting that a more flexible and integrative approach is necessary to maximize their impact on civic and political education.

One of the strategies that has gained relevance is the open classroom, characterized by the creation of spaces for debate that encourage cognitive activation and independent thinking. [25] highlights that, while these strategies can motivate students to become more interested in political issues, they do not always succeed in significantly transforming their understanding of politics. This suggests that, although the open classroom facilitates the development of critical thinking, its impact on substantive knowledge may be limited.

Similarly, the concept of the political classroom has been analyzed by [26], finding that educators often limit deliberations on controversial topics due to their positions, thus restricting the exploration of current political issues. Although the political classroom is seen as a potential space for cultural exchange and political discussion, the role of educators can, paradoxically, hinder the development of a robust civic education.

In the context of political simulations, [27] evaluates a simulation conducted in the UK in 2016, finding that these activities can significantly increase participants' interest in and understanding of politics and the functioning of entities such as the European Union. These results suggest that political simulations are effective tools for connecting students with practical politics, although their impact may depend on the quality of the simulation and the educational context. On the other hand, [28] examines the Barnas program Valg in Norway, which seeks to promote political participation among children. Despite efforts to open spaces for participation, a perception of separation between adult and child political processes persists, indicating that while these initiatives are valuable, there are still challenges to fully integrating young people into formal political processes.

The analysis of the design and application of learning models for the quality of political teaching carried out in [29] provides a quantitative perspective on the effectiveness of different pedagogical approaches. The experimental results indicate significant improvements in students' academic performance and innovative thinking, highlighting the potential of these models to improve political teaching.

Critical pedagogies have also gained prominence. [30] investigates the use of theatre of the oppressed in a neoliberal school setting in England, finding that although this pedagogy fosters engagement and critical reflection among students, its development is limited by neoliberal institutional policies. Nevertheless, students demonstrated significant engagement with learning, suggesting that such approaches can be transformative within appropriate school settings.

In India, [31] studied the implementation of global south pedagogies in early childhood education, highlighting the importance of incorporating political education experiences from an early age. Findings indicate that children approach politics differently than adults, influenced by non-hegemonic contexts, highlighting the need to acknowledge and validate their political experiences.

Taken together, these studies show that pedagogical strategies and educational methodologies are part of the processes of forming students' political and civic attitudes. However, they also reveal the structural and contextual limitations that can restrict their effectiveness, highlighting the need for more integrative and flexible approaches that recognize the complexities of political learning in diverse educational contexts.

3.6 Conclusions of pedagogical strategies and educational methodologies for civic education

The studies considered within this theme highlight that innovative and participatory pedagogical approaches, such as critical pedagogies and collaborative learning, can strengthen students' civic and political education by fostering their political interest and civic skills. These investigations, which mainly employ qualitative methodologies such as creative workshops, participatory observation, and action-research projects, allow for an in-depth analysis of power dynamics in the classroom and students' perceptions of agency and belonging.

However, limitations such as institutional resistance, lack of resources, and restrictions imposed by standardized curricula and traditional assessments can hinder the effective implementation of these innovative methodologies in educational contexts. Despite these challenges, the findings suggest that pedagogical strategies centered on social justice and critical thinking have great potential to transform civic education, promoting meaningful learning and greater political engagement among young people.

3.7 Educational policies and sociopolitical structures: Influences on civic formation

This series of studies investigates how educational policies and socio-political contexts affect students' citizenship formation and civic development. Through different approaches and contexts, the importance of strengthening democratic education and citizen participation is evident, while promoting the development of critical thinking at both the community and personal levels. However, the studies also highlight the limitations and contradictions that educational systems face when trying to balance these objectives with the demands of existing policies and socio-political structures.

In [32] the need to strengthen the basic concepts of democratic education and civic participation by increasing critical thinking on educational and social issues is highlighted. In their analysis, the authors emphasize that teachers are instrumental in strengthening critical thinking among students, pointing out that although there is educational regulation in the Netherlands for politics, democracy, and youth participation, significant weaknesses persist in the content of civic education legislation and its incorporation into the national curriculum. Furthermore, they mention the lack of clarity in the definition of the principles of civic education and the insufficient training of teachers, which hinders the effective implementation of a robust civic education.

[10] addresses the historical development of Civic, Social, and Political Education CSPE and reveals the difficulties in giving it relevance within the educational system. Their study shows a low appreciation of this subject, aggravated by the lack of autonomy of teachers and insufficient teacher training in this area, which hinders its development and effectiveness in schools.

On the other hand, [9] analyzes how political education is affected by contemporary global phenomena, particularly the resurgence of the extreme right and its implications for marginalized populations, such as black communities. They highlight that policies and actions against these communities, inherited from historical practices such as slavery, continue to manifest themselves today, indicating the ongoing need for an education that addresses and challenges these dynamics of power and exclusion.

In a similar vein, [33] explores how globalization and 21st-century educational policies impact critical literacy. They argue that the ideas of democratic citizenship that should underpin critical literacy are threatened by the interests of a neoliberal state system that permeates the educational curriculum. This tension between expectations of forming critical citizens and the imposition of neoliberal ideologies within the educational system creates a contradictory environment for educators and students.

The contradictions inherent in citizenship education under contexts of conflict and neoliberal policies are investigated in [34]. Although teachers are recognized for their crucial role in promoting active and critical citizenship, they face the paradox of having to teach a curriculum that fosters critical thinking while being expected to align their teaching with the ideals of the State, which in many cases adopts neoliberal characteristics. This study highlights the complexities and challenges teachers face in their attempt to navigate and resist imposed educational structures.

[35] explores how educational policies affect the formation of cognitive and affective-behavioral citizenship in low-income youth. The authors find that a lack of resources and family support contributes to lower levels of civic awareness and political participation, emphasizing the need for educational policies that address these socioeconomic disparities and promote more equitable citizenship. [36] presents an analysis of a case study in Canada on pedagogy in civics classes, finding that educational practices can be contradictory. Although a critical understanding of social phenomena is encouraged, teaching sometimes reinforces dominant ideologies, which can lead to student alienation from established learning objectives. This study highlights the importance of aligning pedagogical practice with the goals of promoting critical and reflective citizenship.

Taken together, these studies highlight the tensions and challenges present in contemporary civic education, especially in contexts influenced by neoliberal policies and global socio-political dynamics. They underline the need for a more inclusive and critical educational approach that truly prepares students to take an active part in a democratic society.

3.8 Conclusions of educational policies and sociopolitical structures: influences on civic formation

The reviewed studies highlight several key aspects related to how educational policies, especially those framed in neoliberal and public management contexts, tend to reproduce social inequalities and affect citizenship formation by emphasizing competition and efficiency over equity and social justice. The methods used in these studies are predominantly qualitative, including policy analysis, case studies, and interviews with educational actors, allowing for a deep understanding of participants' experiences and perceptions. However, a significant limitation of this research is its focus on specific contexts, which may limit the generalizability of the results to other regions or educational systems. Furthermore, the reliance on qualitative methods could bias the results toward subjective interpretations of educational policies and their effects. Taken together, these studies underscore the need for more inclusive educational policies that promote social justice and equity in citizenship formation, better adapting to the sociopolitical realities of educational communities.

3.9 Towards a critical consciousness: Training for social justice in educational contexts

In response to the need to transform societies through more active and conscious political participation, various pedagogical strategies have been implemented designed to maximize young people's attention and involvement in political issues. Among these strategies, electoral simulations and in-depth courses stand out, the application of which has given rise to significant research seeking to evaluate their impact on the formation of a critical conscience and commitment to social justice.

The development of critical consciousness among Mexican-American youth through a social justice course is investigated in [37], finding that students who participate in educational environments that value social justice and foster critical consciousness experience significant benefits. The results of this study show that students not only changed their perspectives but also developed skills to claim social justice and promote changes both in their lives and in their communities. This finding denotes the importance of having educators committed to forming students' critical consciousness, highlighting how a social justice-centered education can impact youth to become agents of change.

Conventional representations of young people in the context of political participation and voting rights are challenged in [38] by arguing that these representations, which often cast young people as politically immature or incapable of proper judgment, are used to justify the exclusion of young people from

democratic processes. By challenging these perceptions, [38] argues for the inclusion of young people as full citizens with the right to vote and actively participate in democracy. This approach aligns with the category by promoting a critical consciousness that rejects limiting narratives and advocates for greater social justice, recognizing young people as competent political actors.

[39] analyses how discursive school practices influence young people's perception of democracy. Their study highlights that students tend to differentiate between existing and ideal democracy, showing a critical approach to current democratic structures and underlining the relevance of education in forming a critical consciousness that allows these systems to be questioned and improved. The need for an educational approach that not only informs students about democracy but also fosters knowledge, critical understanding, and action within the framework of democratic values becomes evident.

[40] examines a program at a progressive school in the United States that seeks to develop critical thinking among students. Their findings suggest that although teachers attempt to foster critical skills, they face contradictions in trying to maintain their authoritative role while promoting the autonomy of thought. This study highlights the tensions underlying educational practice between fostering critical thinking and maintaining established power structures, which concludes with the complexity of forming critical consciousness in traditional educational settings.

Recent studies argue that young people are already actively involved in complex political processes and that, therefore, schools should maximize efforts to promote civic education and participation [41]. In this sense, [7] conceives the school as an environment that protects democracy and human rights, and as a fundamental space where students shape their conceptions of what is civic, democratic, and citizen.

These studies show that educational institutions have the potential to become fundamental spaces for the construction of active and critical citizenship. However, they also highlight the need to re-evaluate and strengthen current pedagogical approaches to ensure that they truly empower students to challenge existing power structures and advocate for greater social justice in their communities. The inclusion of critical perspectives, such as those advocated in [38], where the importance of not only teaching about civic participation but also of fighting against the structural barriers that prevent equitable participation of all citizens, including young people, is essential.

3.10 Conclusions of the category Towards a Critical Conscience: Training for Social Justice in Educational Contexts

The reviewed studies highlight the effectiveness of critical pedagogies and action research projects in developing critical consciousness and fostering students' active engagement in social justice. These methodologies enable students to question established power structures and participate in social change, promoting a greater understanding of social rights and environmental sustainability.

However, the implementation of these pedagogies faces significant challenges, such as institutional resistance, lack of resources, and a standardized educational environment, which can limit teachers' ability to implement these approaches effectively. Despite these limitations, research indicates the importance of an educational approach that combines institutional support with innovative pedagogical practices to transform power dynamics in classrooms and prepare students to become drivers of change in their communities.

Table 1. Main results by category

Category	Description	Main results	Relevant studies
Political socialization and school contexts	Exploring how school contexts and social interactions influence students' political subjectivity.	School contexts serve as spaces for political socialization, influencing the formation of political identities.	[1-4, 12-17]
Civic education and citizen participation	Studies that analyze the impact of civic education on citizen	Effective civic education promotes active political participation and civic understanding in students.	[8, 18-24]

	participation and the formation of political attitudes.		
Pedagogical strategies and educational methodologies for civic education	Evaluation of pedagogical practices and educational methodologies to promote critical thinking and civic participation.	Innovative pedagogical methodologies foster critical thinking but face institutional barriers.	[25-31]
Educational policies and socio-political structures	Analysis of the effect of educational policies and sociopolitical contexts on the formation of citizens.	Neoliberal educational policies can limit the formation of critical and equitable citizens.	[9, 32-36]
Towards a critical consciousness: training for social justice in educational contexts	Research on pedagogical strategies to develop critical awareness and commitment to social justice.	Social justice-focused pedagogies foster critical awareness and engagement in social justice.	[7, 37-41]

4. CONCLUSIONS

This literature review has explored the role of schools in the political education of young people, highlighting both the opportunities and challenges faced by educational institutions. From the analysis of various research, several key points can be identified that reflect the complexity of civic and political education in school contexts, as well as the limitations and areas that require further study. The main conclusions drawn from the review are presented below:

- Schools play a fundamental role in the political formation of young people, acting as key spaces where civic identities are constructed and critical attitudes towards civic participation are fostered. Through diverse pedagogical practices and the creation of an educational and democratic environment, educational institutions can foster the development of active and conscious citizenship.
- The effectiveness of these educational practices depends significantly on the institutional context and current educational policies. Policies that prioritize competition and efficiency over equity limit the capacity of schools to promote transformative civic education, often reproducing existing social inequalities.
- In terms of methodologies, most studies employ qualitative approaches, such as interviews and case studies, which allow for an understanding of the experiences and perceptions of educational actors. Although these methods are valuable in capturing the complexity of political socialization in school contexts, they have limitations in terms of generalizability. The lack of quantitative studies limits the possibility of measuring the large-scale impact of educational interventions in different contexts.
- There is a need to expand research on political education in schools and to consider using a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. This will provide a more diverse understanding of educational dynamics and allow for the development of more effective pedagogical policies and practices that better respond to the diverse realities of school, educational, and research communities.

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